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Optimal operations for hydrogen-based energy storage systems in wind farms via model predictive control

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HIGHLIGHTS

- A hydrogen-based ESS model includes several degradation costs of the electrolyzer and fuel cell.
- Degradation costs concern working cycles and life spans of the electrolyzer and fuel cell.
- Features, like warm and cold start, are considered through continuous and logical states combined.
- An MPC controller minimizes the logical state switching between different operating modes.
- The controller meets local load demand and maximizes revenue in the electricity market.

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ABSTRACT

Efficient energy production and consumption are fundamental points for reducing carbon emissions that influence climate change. Alternative resources, such as renewable energy sources (RESs), used in electricity grids, could reduce the environmental impact. Since RESs are inherently unreliable, during the last decades the scientific community addressed research efforts to their integration with the main grid by means of properly designed energy storage systems (ESSs). In order to highlight the best performance from these hybrid systems, proper design and operations are essential. The purpose of this paper is to present a so-called model predictive controller (MPC) for the optimal operations of grid-connected wind farms with hydrogen-based ESSs and local loads. Such MPC has been designed to take into account the operating and economical costs of the ESS, the local load demand and the participation to the electricity market, and further it enforces the fulfillment of the physical and the system's dynamics constraints. The dynamics of the hydrogen-based ESS have been modeled by means of the mixed-logic dynamic (MLD) framework in order to capture different behaviors according to the possible operating modes. The purpose is to provide a controller able to cope both with all the main physical and operating constraints of a hydrogen-based storage system, including the switching among different modes such as ON, OFF, STAND-BY and, at the same time, reduce the management costs and increase the equipment lifesaving. The case study for this paper is a plant under development in the north Norway. Numerical analysis on the related plant

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data shows the effectiveness of the proposed strategy, which manages the plant and commits the equipment so as to preserve the given constraints and save them from unnecessary commutation cycles.

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Nomenclature

Devices parameters

δ	Logical variables according to the device modes
ε	Controller minimum tolerance
η	Charging/discharging efficiency
Γ	Energy price [€/kWh]
C	Hourly cost [€/h]
NH	Cycle life hours device.
NY	The number of working hour per year of device [h]
N	The number of cycles of device [cycles]
ρ	Penalty weighting factors
σ	State transitions of device.
d	Degradation rate of device.
H	Stored level of the hydrogen [kg]
M	Upper bound of the function $P(k)$
m	Lower bound of the function $P(k)$
P	Electric power [kW]
R	Ramp up limits of device [kW/h]
T	Prediction horizon
T_s	Sample time.
z	Auxiliary variables

Subscripts

avl	Available
CLD	Cold-state
dump	Dumped
ez	Electrolyzer
fc	Fuel cell
grid	Main grid
OFF	Off-state
ON	On-state
ref	Reference load
STB	stand-by-state
w	Wind farm.
WRM	Warm-state

Superscripts

$\geq \gamma$	Greater than or equal to γ
$\leq \bar{\gamma}$	Less than or equal to $\bar{\gamma}$
CLD	Cold-state
in	Input
max	Maximum value
min	Minimum value
OFF	Off-state
OM	Operating and maintenance
ON	On-state

out	Output
pch	Purchase of energy
rep	Replacement
sale	Sale of energy
sc	Spot of energy
STB	Stand-by-state
WRM	Warm-state

Variables

$\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \bar{\gamma}, i$	Elements of sets
$\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}, \bar{\mathcal{B}}, \mathcal{I}$	Sets

Introduction

During the last decades, the integration of wind-based renewable energy sources (RESs) in the main grid and their use in the energy market have considerably increased [1]. However, their penetration is prevented by their inherently intermittent nature [2–4]. Among the solutions suggested over the years to mitigate such problems, here we focus our attention on endowing wind farms with hydrogen-based energy storage systems (ESSs) [5–7].

A typical approach is to achieve optimal operations of such ESSs by means of suitable control strategies taking into account different relevant aspects. They include but are not restricted to load demand satisfaction, degradation issues, equipment costs, energy acquisition costs and, in general, energy market participation. In this regard, the model based predictive control (MPC) strategy appears today a powerful technique that allows the simultaneous handling of constraints, delays, system disturbances and the minimization of some desired costs as well.

In general, the control of ESSs is indeed challenging since several aspects can potentially be considered: continuous dynamics related to the electrical system or to the storage charge/discharge can possibly interact with logic dynamics of several devices within the overall plant, allowing a finite number of possible operating modes (such as on, off, stand-by and others device specific) characterized by specific working conditions. In this context, MPC is a technique potentially able to solve such issues and provide the control inputs to safely and efficiently operate the system.

The interested reader can refer to Refs. [8–10] where the MPC based solutions have been proposed for the optimal

dispatch of renewable generation units and demand response in a grid-tied system.

Despite its potentiality and flexibility, the adoption of an MPC strategy requires a deep and thorough modeling study of the plant to be controlled so as to generate a set of equalities and inequalities constraints representing the plant model with respect to the control goals to be achieved. Being the MPC an optimization-based technique, the same care needs to be considered in the design of a suitable cost function representing the objective of the control.

In Section Literature review, several valuable papers are revised where MPC strategies are adopted for different energy and storage plants and different control objectives. From the viewpoint of the energy units, one has to take into account the physical and operating constraints of the different devices and the various working modes (off, on, stand-by, warm and cold start, etc). From the viewpoint of the interconnection with the power grid, several characteristics can be considered such as the possibility to import/export the power to/from the grid with the related costs, the power quality, the demand satisfaction. A relevant problem in controlling ESSs is limiting the degradation of the devices caused not only by the working hours, but also by the working cycles (complete off-on-off cycle). As it will be clear later, the possibility of accounting for these effects has been explored very little in the literature and usually limited to a simple on-off modeling of the devices. The same applies for the related degradation issues and costs.

Combining continuous and logic dynamics and constraints with degradation issues is an important aspect to be taken into account in control strategies for hydrogen-based ESSs since the electrolyzers and fuel cells are usually expensive, an aspect that can harm a widespread adoption of such systems. It is therefore of paramount importance to preserve their working life and operate them appropriately.

In particular, referring to the degradation aspects, electrolyzers and fuel cells have different physical mechanisms. Fluctuations in the current applied to electrolyzers and the fuel cells produce: i) differential pressure variations, reverse conduction of hydrogen to the oxygen separator or vice-versa; ii) small concentrations of hydrogen in oxygen or vice-versa (greater than 4%) leading to explosive reactions; iii) the mechanical wear losses of the membrane; iv) membrane's chemical degradation via radical attack. In electrolyzers, on/off cycling produces: i) temperature and pressure oscillations leading to chemical and mechanical degradations; ii) uncontrolled stack polarity chemical degradation; iii) production of hydrogen peroxide at cathode after turn-off with subsequent membrane and carbon carrier oxidation [11]. In fuel cells, on/off cycling produces: i) potential oscillations leading to catalyzer (platinum) particles dissolving in the cathode; ii) thermal and humidity oscillations leading to membrane mechanical wearing; iii) chemical degradation of the membrane via radical attack during open circuit periods; iv) starvation phenomena when the current drawn from a fuel cell is not in the correct proportion to the reacted oxygen; v) humidity losses in the membrane. Start/stop cycling produces: i) carbon corrosion in the electrodes; ii) catalysis layer deactivation [12].

The motivation of the paper lies exactly in the need of developing dynamical models and a related MPC strategy in

order to thoroughly characterise and control the behaviour of the electrolyzer and the fuel cell.

More specifically, in this paper the optimal commitment of a hydrogen-based ESS paired to a wind farm is investigated. The considered system supplies a local load and forms a microgrid which exchanges power with the grid when connected. In the control strategy, the economic costs and degradations of the hydrogen-based ESS are also considered. Suitable cost functions, linearly combined through proper weights, are defined so as to deal with an intrinsically multi-objective problems. The wind-hydrogen plant is modeled by means of a suitable logic framework called MLD (mixed-logic dynamic) so as to take into account both continuous dynamics and the switching between different working modes. The MLD modeling allows also to incorporate switching and degradation costs of the hydrogen production/consumption devices so that the controller exploits the real capabilities of the devices.

This paper extends the preliminary study presented in Refs. [4,13] by adopting more sophisticated and detailed models of the electrolyzer and the fuel cell. In particular, the cold and warm states have been included which allows for higher fidelity models, easing the control response to abrupt produced/consumed power imbalances and reducing mode switchings, so as to preserve the units from premature degradation. This results in maximizing the operating life of such expensive devices; decreasing the states switching costs; maximizing the revenues related to electricity market participation. The implementation of the real-time MPC is achieved by taking into account the data considered for the HAEOLUS project [14].

The study at hand has significant differences with respect to the relevant literature which, as will be highlighted in Section Literature review, does not include such sophisticated models, as well as the devices' degradation mitigation and working/logical modes, which are key aspect of this manuscript. Specifically, the main contributions of the current work are:

1. Development of a novel dynamic hydrogen-based ESS model that takes into account the electrolyzer and the fuel cell different degradation costs concerning their working cycles and related devices life spans;
2. Combined modelling of continuous dynamics and discrete working modes, including features such as warm and cold start;
3. Implementation of an MPC control strategy that minimizes the switching among different operating modes;
4. Local load demand satisfaction, and at the same time revenue maximization through electricity market participation.

The models and the control strategy presented in this paper have been developed as a part of the EU-FCH 2 JU (European Union Fuel Cells and Hydrogen 2 Joint Undertaking) project HAEOLUS - Hydrogen-Aeolic Energy with Optimized electrolyzers Upstream of Substation [14]. In such a project, a hydrogen-based ESS subject to the proposed control strategy will be integrated into a wind farm located in north Norway. The project will demonstrate the techno-economic feasibility

of the integrated system (wind farm + hydrogen-based ESS) in three different use cases as per the IEA-Task 24 final report [15], and the control strategy that this paper develops will enable the wind farm to operate conforming to the mini-grid use case. Numerical simulations are performed to demonstrate the applicability and feasibility of the approach proposed against data taken from the project and, for those parts not yet designed, complemented with data taken from the literature. With respect to the economic profitability analysis of the proposed plant (not control related aspects), the reader is referred to Ref. [16].

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: in Section Literature review, relevant papers from the literature will be revised. In Section Material and methods, the material and methods are explained in detail. In Section Results analysis and discussion, the validation of the results through simulation examples is provided, while the concluding remarks and further discussion are given in Section Conclusions.

Literature review

MPC strategies for energy plants and ESSs have been studied by several papers in the literature referring to different control goals and systems characteristics. For instance, with respect to the user demand satisfaction, Torreglosa et al. in Ref. [17] presented an MPC based energy dispatching algorithm for off-grid hybrid systems. The MPC generates the electrolyzer and the fuel cell power references in order to satisfy the requested load demand by the user, and at the same time to respect the devices upper and lower bound charge constraints. Maghami et al. in Ref. [18] developed a novel off-grid energy management strategy to control the power flow among the hydrogen system and power supply components to meet the load demand. Further, their study proposed the reduction in peak demand, system cost minimization and also surplus power generation extraction beyond the rate of the battery. In Wang et al. [19], the MPC scheme for operating an off-grid hybrid ESSs with a fuel cell and an ultracapacitor is proposed to satisfy the requested load demand by the user. Petrollese et al. in Ref. [20] developed an MPC-based EMS which optimizes the planning of a microgrid comprising renewable energy units, batteries and hydrogen storage systems. The MPC control strategy developed is able to satisfy the electrical references with proper utilization of the hybrid storage systems (battery for short-term and hydrogen for long-term storage) while reducing the microgrid operating costs. However, the optimization problems in the above mentioned studies do not take into account the degradation process of the expensive equipment (the electrolyzer and the fuel cell).

The electrolyzer and the fuel cell degradation have been addressed in other studies, as for instance in Refs. [21–24], where the authors investigated how they are affected by load fluctuations or start-up/shut-down cycles. Then, the degradation issues are taken into account by means of suitable models that are included into the proposed algorithms. However, these models do not incorporate further operational modes (and the related power consumption), such as the stand-by or the warm and cold start. In Ref. [25], Cecilia et al.

presented an MPC scheme for a hybrid hydrogen-based ESS, but the dependency of the degradation on the switching cycles (both on the power and the working hours) is not considered.

With respect to energy cost aspects, Valverde et al. in Ref. [26] addressed them by considering those related to the electricity export/import to/from the grid, the costs due to components aging, and the maintenance and operational costs. Then, they designed a control strategy to satisfy the requested electric demand, and at the same time to extend the lifespan of the equipment. The application scenario is a laboratory scaled microgrid where the proposed control system is able to minimize the overall costs of the hydrogen-based microgrid. However, neither the authors consider the equipment's capital costs or they consider the devices' different operating conditions at run time (e.g., on, off, stand-by).

With the provision of energy market participation, in Ref. [21] Garcia-Torres et al. presented the economic schedule of a network of interconnected microgrids for energy market participation with hybrid ESS under failure conditions. The authors developed and validated the ESS using MPC. Daneshvar et al. in Ref. [27] presented an optimal stochastic day-ahead energy market scheduling for the hydrogen-based microgrids with 100% RESs taking into account the economic and environmental aspects. To achieve this, 10 hydrogen-based microgrids were operated in order to meet a large portion of energy load through carbon-free and cost-effective energy generation systems. Each microgrid was equipped with a photo-voltaic (PV) system, a wind turbine (WT) and a hybrid hydrogen ESS and could exchange energy within the day-ahead market. Mendes et al. in Ref. [3] presented an MPC controller for the optimal energy management of a renewable powered microgrid with utility grid interconnection. The authors proposed a two layers control architecture which addresses the system management at different time scales. In particular, the microgrid stability is achieved at the first layer, while the participation to the energy market is managed at the second layer, where also the optimal use of the RESs, the ESSs and the optimal recharge scheduling of electric vehicles are considered. Among the different contributions provided, this paper shows the importance of the MPC technique for the achievement of optimal economic energy flow management in renewable energy microgrids. All the above mentioned authors adopted relatively simple models for the ESS lifetime maximization. Also, they simply considered on/off working modes, neglecting possible other ones like stand-by and related cold and warm start.

Beyond the reported literature, it is possible to find a wide range of papers where MPC, also in combination with other advanced techniques, is used for the optimal operations of energy systems. For instance, Gonzalez et al. in Ref. [10] presented an MPC-based coordinated scheduling framework to regulate the state of charge of a hybrid ESS under variable wind and grid demand scenarios. The authors proposed a look-ahead optimization policy between the wind farm and the ESS to determine the injected net power to the grid. The reported benefits of the proposed study are the combined profit of the wind generation and the storage systems, and the smoothing of wind farm net power injection into the grid. However, the authors do not considered the ESS operating and

maintenance costs. In Ref. [28], Zhang et al. implemented an MPC controller to optimally schedule and control the hybrid co-generation power systems for large scale RESs with the mixed-logic dynamic (MLD) representation. The MLD framework along with the MPC scheme is applied to distributed energy resources with a battery-based ESS in Ref. [29]. However, the authors do not take into account other kinds of ESS nor battery degradation. In Refs. [26,30], Bonthu et al. and Velarde et al. developed MPC strategies for microgrid optimization similarly to those in Refs. [31–33] where mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) is used and the ESS operational costs are included.

Further to the above, the optimal performances can be related to the more general techno-economic performance of energy systems [34]. For instance, in Ref. [35] Awan et al. addressed the techno-economic analysis of a hybrid ESS including batteries, pumped hydro, and hydrogen-based storages, however still neglecting the ESSs degradation issue. Coppitters et al. in Ref. [36] presented a computationally efficient robust control strategy for the optimization of a hydrogen-based microgrid under different scenarios. The paper provides a robust optimization design by taking into account the techno-economic uncertainties of the hydrogen-based plants. The above cited studies lack in providing detailed models for the targeted ESSs, which would improve the reliability of the results.

Besides the optimal control schemes, it is also possible to find in the literature heuristics and meta-heuristics approaches. In particular, a partial search algorithm may provide an acceptably good solution to the optimization problem. The most adopted heuristic algorithms in the literature includes genetic algorithm (GA), simulated annealing (SA), particle swarm optimization (PSO), ant colony optimization (ACO) and duelist algorithm (DA). Eteiba et al. in Ref. [37] conducted a techno-economic analysis of an off-grid PV hybrid system by using flower pollination algorithm (FPA), the harmony search (HS) algorithm, the artificial bee colony (ABC) algorithm and the firefly algorithm (FA). The ultimate objective was to determine an optimal solution for the sizing problem. Barakat et al. in Ref. [38] presented a feasibility study for grid-tied RESs (PV and biomass) system designed to feed the electrical load of a village situated in Beni-Suef, Egypt. The authors analyzed the electric demand of the village considering environmental and economic aspects. The system has been optimized through HOMER optimization toolbox and showed that the grid connected PV-biomass system was the most effective way of reducing carbon emissions. Sammy et al. studied in Refs. [34,39,40] the island combined renewable energy systems using combinations of PV/FC (fuel cell), PV/WT/FC, and WT/FC with frog leaping algorithm (FLA) and the PSO. The result shows that the output from the solar PV/WT/FC combination along with the hydrogen production systems grants excellent performance. Moreover, in Ref. [41], the authors also studied an off-grid renewable (PV and Biomass) energy system by implementing a hybrid approach (invasive weed optimization and PSO), to meet the electric demand of a fruit farm located in the new city of Borg El-Arab in Alexandria, Egypt. The authors also compared the results of this study with the other meta-heuristics approaches such as PSO and FPA. Mokhtar et al. studied in Ref. [42] a sector coupling strategy

(building and transportation) using a meta-heuristic PSO in order to maximize the self-sufficiency of a University campus in Ouargla, Algeria to produce power and hydrogen.

Contrarily to the above revised papers, this work does not adopt heuristic methods while it solves mixed-integer optimal problems by means of numerical commercial solvers. Through numerical analysis, it is showed that the derived control problem is solvable within the considered sampling intervals.

The valuable literature revised either does not take into account the expensive equipment costs or, if it does, the ESSs degradation models considered for this purpose are oversimplified. This is one of the key aspects studied in this paper, which focuses on the hydrogen-based ESS modeling both in its operating constraints and equipment working modes/cycles. The low-level/local control of WTs is out of the scope of the study and is instead assumed already operating on the wind farm.

Material and methods

Background

Essential background concepts and methodology on MPC are here provided, to be adopted in the modeling and control of the plant at hand, where specific equations will be derived and presented.

The MPC control was originally designed for the process control industry, characterized by slow dynamic systems, but it gained the attention of a wider control engineering community in the last decades thanks to the availability of high performance computer systems. For a rigorous dissertation of the MPC the interested reader is directed to the referred literature, see for example [4,43]. Roughly speaking, the MPC consists in formulating a control problem as an optimization problem over a finite time horizon and iteratively solves it at each sampling time while the horizon “recedes”. Specifically, given a dynamical described by the discrete-time model

$$x(k+1) = f(x(k), u(k)), \quad (1)$$

with state $x(k) \in \mathcal{X}_k \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$, input $u(k) \in \mathcal{U}_k \subseteq \mathbb{R}^m$, initial condition $x(0) \in \mathcal{X}_0$, and a cost function $J(x(k), u(k))$, the method is based on searching, at each time k , the optimal input sequence over a receding time horizon of duration T , i.e. $\mathbf{u}_k^{T-1} = \{u(k), u(k+1), \dots, u(k+T-1)\}$, according to

$$\mathbf{u}_k^* = \arg \min_{\mathbf{u}_k^{T-1}} \sum_{j=0}^{T-1} J(x(k+j), u(k+j))$$

s.t.

$$x(k+j+1) = f(x(k+j), u(k+j)), \quad (2)$$

$$x(k+j) \in \mathcal{X}_{k+j}, \quad \text{for } j = 1, \dots, T-1,$$

$$u(k+j) \in \mathcal{U}_{k+j}, \quad \text{for } j = 0, \dots, T-1,$$

$x(0)$ measured from the plant.

After computing \mathbf{u}_k^{T-1} , its first component $u(k)$ is fed to the system, then the time advances by one step to $k+1$ and the procedure is iterated, thus also implementing a feedback

policy. The problem (2) is usually solved through optimization techniques implemented by numerical solvers.

The MPC is potentially able to incorporate hybrid/discontinuous dynamics, logical or integer decision variables and operating constraints such as working ranges, physical limits, time delays or time deadzones. On the other hand, the method requires a good modeling of the plant, which may be a nontrivial task for complex systems or plants. In what follows, the modeling of the problem addressed and its resolution via an MPC approach is carefully provided and solved as a key contribution of the paper.

The mixed logic inequality formulation will be developed according to the theory presented in Ref. [44].

System description, modeling, and constraints

This subsection provides the hydrogen-based ESS models developed in this study, specifically: discrete state logic dynamics; operating and physical constraints; continuous dynamics. Such constraints will be all included within the proposed controller. Nevertheless, their generality allows employment on plants with different components than the one here analysed.

Notation

Boolean variables assume either false (denoted with 0) or true (denoted with 1) values. Lowercase non-bold letters denote scalars; lowercase bold letters represent column vectors; uppercase non-bold letters denote matrices and the set of the real numbers is \mathbb{R} . Furthermore, throughout the paper, an indexing with respect to the electrolyzer (ez) and the fuel cell (fc) will be used by means of $i \in \mathcal{I} = \{ez, fc\}$. In addition, the sets $\mathcal{A} = \{\text{OFF}, \text{CLD}, \text{STB}, \text{WRM}, \text{ON}\}$, $\mathcal{S} = \{0, p_i^{\text{CLD}}, p_i^{\text{STB}}, p_i^{\text{WRM}}, p_i^{\text{min}}\}$, $\mathcal{T} = \{0, p_i^{\text{CLD}}, p_i^{\text{STB}}, p_i^{\text{WRM}}, p_i^{\text{max}}\}$ and $\mathcal{P} = \{(\gamma, \bar{\gamma}) \mid (\gamma = \bar{\gamma}) \vee (\gamma = p_i^{\text{min}} \wedge \bar{\gamma} = p_i^{\text{max}}), \gamma \in \mathcal{S}, \bar{\gamma} \in \mathcal{T}\}^2$ are introduced in order to achieve more compact descriptions. Moreover, $\alpha \neq \beta$ is always assumed whenever $\alpha, \beta \in \mathcal{A}$.

In the paper, formulas are expressed with respect to discrete time k . The continuous time t is related through $t = kT_s$, with T_s being the sampling time.

Microgrid description

The wind-hydrogen plant under study is illustrated in Fig. 1. The power flow, the hydrogen flow, and the data flow are denoted by green, blue, and red lines, respectively. In an ideal scenario, the reference demand will be met directly from P_w . In that case, the hydrogen-based ESS is not operated. Nevertheless, in real operating conditions, the excess power by wind generation is stored in the hydrogen tank via electrolysis; the hydrogen can be re-electrified by the fuel cell during low wind hours. The handling of such storage/retrieve mechanism, together with the models described in what follows, are the core contribution of the paper.

In the considered scenario, the local load reference demand P_{ref} , given as input to the controller, is provided by an external system.

Fig. 1 – Microgrid under investigation. $P_{\text{ez}}^{\text{ON}}$ is the electrolyzer input power, $P_{\text{fc}}^{\text{ON}}$ represents the fuel cell output power, P_w is the wind power, P_{grid} indicates the grid power, P_{dump} is the dumped power and P_{ref} is the local load reference demand tracked by P_{avl} .

Fig. 2 – Operational modes sequential graph of the $i \in \{ez, fc\}$ device.

The electrolyzer and the fuel cell can be operated in three different physical modes, namely the on, the off and the stand-by modes. As shown in Fig. 2, this fact can be modeled, separately for the electrolyzer and the fuel cell, by means of two automata with five states: the ON, the OFF and the STB modes and two additional modes, the CLD and the WRM, to account for cold and warm starts. The proposed MPC controller will have to determine when to switch off or put in stand-by the devices according to a trade-off among cold start, warm start and operations in stand-by, the latter requiring a constant power supply even with null production/consumption [14].

Each state of the automata is linked to a logic variable³ $\delta_i^\alpha(k) \in [0, 1]$, where $\alpha \in \mathcal{A}$, so that $\delta_i^\alpha(k) = 1$ whenever for a given $i \in \{ez, fc\}$, the corresponding i automaton is in state α at time-step k , $\delta_i^\alpha(k) = 0$ otherwise. Similarly, each edge is also linked to a logic variable $\sigma_{\alpha,i}^\beta(k) \in [0, 1]$, so that $\sigma_{\alpha,i}^\beta(k) = 1$ whenever the i automaton is switching from the state α to the state β at time-step k , $\sigma_{\alpha,i}^\beta(k) = 0$ otherwise. As it will be clearer later, the transitions affecting the operating costs of the electrolyzer and the fuel cell are among the states ON–OFF, CLD–STB and STB–OFF, since they cumulatively account for

³ Both the variable δ_i^α and $\sigma_{\alpha,i}^\beta$ includes in the MLD formulation of the study are defined in the whole interval $[0, 1]$. The constraints introduced later will force them to take values only at the boundaries of the interval.

² \wedge and \vee stand for the AND and OR logical operators.

a complete operational cycle and, therefore, affect the cycles lifespan of each device.

Logical states and MLD constraints

The five states automata reported in Fig. 2 will be modeled through an MLD formulation. The states OFF, CLD, STB, WRM and ON of each device's automaton are characterized by the "mixed" product between the pertaining logical variable and the nonzero power corresponding to that discrete state. To explain this concept, let us examine the electrolyzer in its ON state. The corresponding input power for the ON state P_{ez}^{in} is bounded within $[P_{ez}^{min}, P_{ez}^{max}]$. Thus, by defining $P_{ez}^{in} = P_{ez}(k)\delta_{ez}^{ON}(k)$ it results $P_{ez}^{in} = P_{ez}(k) \in [P_{ez}^{min}, P_{ez}^{max}]$ when $\delta_{ez}^{ON}(k) = 1$. In addition, being mutually exclusive, all other logical variables $\delta_{ez}^{\alpha}(k)$, with $\alpha \neq ON$, are null.

In STB state the corresponding relevant power is P_{ez}^{STB} . Therefore, by defining $P_{ez}^{STB} = P_{ez}(k)\delta_{ez}^{STB}(k)$ it follows that $P_{ez}^{STB} = P_{ez}(k)$ since accordingly $\delta_{ez}^{STB}(k) = 1$. Again, all other logical variables $\delta_{ez}^{\alpha}(k)$ are null. Similar considerations can be carried out for the WRM and CLD states. Finally, the electrolyzer in the OFF state yields $P_{ez}(k) = 0$, since no hydrogen is produced in this status and the power consumption is null. In general $P_i^{\alpha} = P_i\delta_i^{\alpha}(k)$, therefore, according to the operating condition of the $i \in \{ez, fc\}$ -th device, each $\delta_i^{\alpha}(k)$ is determined as

$$\begin{cases} P_i^{min} \leq P_i(k) \leq P_i^{max} & \Leftrightarrow \delta_i^{ON} = 1, \\ P_i(k) = P_i^{CLD} & \Leftrightarrow \delta_i^{CLD} = 1, \\ P_i(k) = P_i^{STB} & \Leftrightarrow \delta_i^{STB} = 1, \\ P_i(k) = P_i^{WRM} & \Leftrightarrow \delta_i^{WRM} = 1, \\ P_i(k) = 0 & \Leftrightarrow \delta_i^{OFF} = 1. \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

The modeling approach followed in this paper consists in deriving a mixed-integer formulation of the operating constraints and logical device states so as to be included in a MPC controller and solved by suitable numerical optimization toolboxes. The logical expressions in (3) cannot be handled by such numerical solvers as they are; instead, they require further manipulations to derive equivalent mixed-integer inequalities by introducing auxiliary Boolean variables defined as

$$z_i^{\geq 0}(k) = \begin{cases} 1 & P_i(k) \geq 0, \\ 0 & P_i(k) < 0, \end{cases} \quad (4a)$$

$$z_i^{\leq 0}(k) = \begin{cases} 0 & P_i(k) > 0, \\ 1 & P_i(k) \leq 0, \end{cases} \quad (4b)$$

$$z_i^{\geq P_i^{CLD}}(k) = \begin{cases} 1 & P_i(k) \geq P_i^{CLD}, \\ 0 & P_i(k) < P_i^{CLD}, \end{cases} \quad (4c)$$

$$z_i^{\leq P_i^{CLD}}(k) = \begin{cases} 0 & P_i(k) > P_i^{CLD}, \\ 1 & P_i(k) \leq P_i^{CLD}, \end{cases} \quad (4d)$$

$$z_i^{\geq P_i^{STB}}(k) = \begin{cases} 1 & P_i(k) \geq P_i^{STB}, \\ 0 & P_i(k) < P_i^{STB}, \end{cases} \quad (4e)$$

$$z_i^{\leq P_i^{STB}}(k) = \begin{cases} 0 & P_i(k) > P_i^{STB}, \\ 1 & P_i(k) \leq P_i^{STB}, \end{cases} \quad (4f)$$

$$z_i^{\geq P_i^{WRM}}(k) = \begin{cases} 1 & P_i(k) \geq P_i^{WRM}, \\ 0 & P_i(k) < P_i^{WRM}, \end{cases} \quad (4g)$$

$$z_i^{\leq P_i^{WRM}}(k) = \begin{cases} 0 & P_i(k) > P_i^{WRM}, \\ 1 & P_i(k) \leq P_i^{WRM}, \end{cases} \quad (4h)$$

$$z_i^{\geq P_i^{min}}(k) = \begin{cases} 1 & P_i(k) \geq P_i^{min}, \\ 0 & P_i(k) < P_i^{min}, \end{cases} \quad (4i)$$

$$z_i^{\leq P_i^{max}}(k) = \begin{cases} 0 & P_i(k) > P_i^{max}, \\ 1 & P_i(k) \leq P_i^{max}. \end{cases} \quad (4j)$$

By using the transformations defined in Ref. [44], the above formulas can be expressed through the following inequalities constraints for each case:

$$P_i(k) < Mz_i^{\geq 0}(k), -P_i(k) \leq M(1 - z_i^{\geq 0}(k)); \quad (5a)$$

$$-P_i(k) < Mz_i^{\leq 0}(k), P_i(k) \leq M(1 - z_i^{\leq 0}(k)); \quad (5b)$$

$$P_i(k) - P_i^{CLD} < Mz_i^{\geq P_i^{CLD}}(k), -P_i(k) + P_i^{CLD} \leq M(1 - z_i^{\geq P_i^{CLD}}(k)); \quad (5c)$$

$$-P_i(k) + P_i^{CLD} < Mz_i^{\leq P_i^{CLD}}(k), P_i(k) - P_i^{CLD} \leq M(1 - z_i^{\leq P_i^{CLD}}(k)); \quad (5d)$$

$$P_i(k) - P_i^{STB} < Mz_i^{\geq P_i^{STB}}(k), -P_i(k) + P_i^{STB} \leq M(1 - z_i^{\geq P_i^{STB}}(k)); \quad (5e)$$

$$-P_i(k) + P_i^{STB} < Mz_i^{\leq P_i^{STB}}(k), P_i(k) - P_i^{STB} \leq M(1 - z_i^{\leq P_i^{STB}}(k)); \quad (5f)$$

$$P_i(k) - P_i^{WRM} < Mz_i^{\geq P_i^{WRM}}(k), -P_i(k) + P_i^{WRM} \leq M(1 - z_i^{\geq P_i^{WRM}}(k)); \quad (5g)$$

$$-P_i(k) + P_i^{WRM} < Mz_i^{\leq P_i^{WRM}}(k), P_i(k) - P_i^{WRM} \leq M(1 - z_i^{\leq P_i^{WRM}}(k)); \quad (5h)$$

$$P_i(k) - P_i^{min} < Mz_i^{\geq P_i^{min}}(k), -P_i(k) + P_i^{min} \leq M(1 - z_i^{\geq P_i^{min}}(k)); \quad (5i)$$

$$-P_i(k) + P_i^{max} < Mz_i^{\leq P_i^{max}}(k), P_i(k) - P_i^{max} \leq M(1 - z_i^{\leq P_i^{max}}(k)). \quad (5j)$$

In order to achieve an MLD model which combines the discrete logical states of the devices with their corresponding operating powers, according to (3), the auxiliary Boolean variables constrained by the inequalities in (5) are exploited. Specifically, the logical variables δ_i^{α} can be determined by linking the inequalities involving $z_i^{\geq \gamma}$ and $z_i^{\leq \bar{\gamma}}$ for each $i \in \{ez, fc\}$ such that the devices will be in one and only one state at a time with respect to the power characterizing its corresponding logical state. The following constraints are therefore derived

$$(1 - \delta_i^{\text{ON}}(k)) + Z_i^{\geq p_i^{\text{min}}} (k) \geq 1, \quad (6a)$$

$$(1 - \delta_i^{\text{ON}}(k)) + Z_i^{\leq p_i^{\text{max}}} (k) \geq 1, \quad (6b)$$

$$(1 - \delta_i^{\text{CLD}}(k)) + Z_i^{\geq p_i^{\text{CLD}}} (k) \geq 1, \quad (6c)$$

$$(1 - \delta_i^{\text{CLD}}(k)) + Z_i^{\leq p_i^{\text{CLD}}} (k) \geq 1, \quad (6d)$$

$$(1 - \delta_i^{\text{STB}}(k)) + Z_i^{\geq p_i^{\text{STB}}} (k) \geq 1, \quad (6e)$$

$$(1 - \delta_i^{\text{STB}}(k)) + Z_i^{\leq p_i^{\text{STB}}} (k) \geq 1, \quad (6f)$$

$$(1 - \delta_i^{\text{WRM}}(k)) + Z_i^{\geq p_i^{\text{WRM}}} (k) \geq 1, \quad (6g)$$

$$(1 - \delta_i^{\text{WRM}}(k)) + Z_i^{\leq p_i^{\text{WRM}}} (k) \geq 1, \quad (6h)$$

$$(1 - \delta_i^{\text{OFF}}(k)) + Z_i^{\geq 0} (k) \geq 1, \quad (6i)$$

$$(1 - \delta_i^{\text{OFF}}(k)) + Z_i^{\leq 0} (k) \geq 1. \quad (6j)$$

Since the devices will work in one and only one mode at each time k , the additional constraint has to be considered.

$$\delta_i^{\text{OFF}}(k) + \delta_i^{\text{CLD}}(k) + \delta_i^{\text{STB}}(k) + \delta_i^{\text{WRM}}(k) + \delta_i^{\text{ON}}(k) = 1 \quad (7)$$

From the above sets of constraints (5)–(7), if, for example, the power of the device $i \in \{\text{ez, fc}\}$ is $P_i \in [P_i^{\text{min}}, P_i^{\text{max}}]$, then only δ_i^{ON} will be 1 and vice versa, while the other logical variables will be null. Similar considerations apply to the other states. Here it is important to highlight that the devices operate independently of each other and no mutually exclusive constraint has been enforced. So, it may happen that the electrolyzer and the fuel cell are both ON at the same time. Such a feature will be handled directly by the controller which could decide to operate the plant keeping only one of them producing/consuming hydrogen or keeping them both operating if, under particular circumstances, the cost incurred in producing and consuming hydrogen at the same time is lower than enforcing a switching ON-OFF cycle to one of the devices.

MLD constraints of the state transitions

As discussed above, the transitions among states can be modeled by means of corresponding logical variables with standard logical connectives. Given the number of states, twenty transitions are ideally possible (Fig. 2). However, only those transitions affecting the operating costs of the electrolyzer and of the fuel cell in the device operation need to be considered in the controller objective function, while all the inadmissible transitions are set to 0. Considering that the allowed transitions are reported in Fig. 2, the resulting sixteen transitions are modeled

$$\sigma_{\text{OFF},i}^{\text{ON}}(k) = \delta_i^{\text{OFF}}(k-1) \wedge \delta_i^{\text{ON}}(k), \quad (8a)$$

$$\sigma_{\text{OFF},i}^{\text{WRM}}(k) = \delta_i^{\text{OFF}}(k-1) \wedge \delta_i^{\text{WRM}}(k), \quad (8b)$$

$$\sigma_{\text{OFF},i}^{\text{STB}}(k) = \delta_i^{\text{OFF}}(k-1) \wedge \delta_i^{\text{STB}}(k), \quad (8c)$$

$$\sigma_{\text{CLD},i}^{\text{OFF}}(k) = \delta_i^{\text{CLD}}(k-1) \wedge \delta_i^{\text{OFF}}(k), \quad (8d)$$

$$\sigma_{\text{CLD},i}^{\text{ON}}(k) = \delta_i^{\text{CLD}}(k-1) \wedge \delta_i^{\text{ON}}(k), \quad (8e)$$

$$\sigma_{\text{CLD},i}^{\text{WRM}}(k) = \delta_i^{\text{CLD}}(k-1) \wedge \delta_i^{\text{WRM}}(k), \quad (8f)$$

$$\sigma_{\text{STB},i}^{\text{ON}}(k) = \delta_i^{\text{STB}}(k-1) \wedge \delta_i^{\text{ON}}(k), \quad (8g)$$

$$\sigma_{\text{STB},i}^{\text{CLD}}(k) = \delta_i^{\text{STB}}(k-1) \wedge \delta_i^{\text{CLD}}(k), \quad (8h)$$

$$\sigma_{\text{WRM},i}^{\text{OFF}}(k) = \delta_i^{\text{WRM}}(k-1) \wedge \delta_i^{\text{OFF}}(k), \quad (8i)$$

$$\sigma_{\text{WRM},i}^{\text{CLD}}(k) = \delta_i^{\text{WRM}}(k-1) \wedge \delta_i^{\text{CLD}}(k), \quad (8j)$$

$$\sigma_{\text{WRM},i}^{\text{STB}}(k) = \delta_i^{\text{WRM}}(k-1) \wedge \delta_i^{\text{STB}}(k), \quad (8k)$$

$$\sigma_{\text{ON},i}^{\text{CLD}}(k) = \delta_i^{\text{ON}}(k-1) \wedge \delta_i^{\text{CLD}}(k), \quad (8l)$$

$$\sigma_{\text{ON},i}^{\text{WRM}}(k) = \delta_i^{\text{ON}}(k-1) \wedge \delta_i^{\text{WRM}}(k), \quad (8m)$$

$$\sigma_{\text{CLD},i}^{\text{STB}}(k) = \delta_i^{\text{CLD}}(k-1) \wedge \delta_i^{\text{STB}}(k), \quad (8n)$$

$$\sigma_{\text{STB},i}^{\text{OFF}}(k) = \delta_i^{\text{STB}}(k-1) \wedge \delta_i^{\text{OFF}}(k), \quad (8o)$$

$$\sigma_{\text{ON},i}^{\text{OFF}}(k) = \delta_i^{\text{ON}}(k-1) \wedge \delta_i^{\text{OFF}}(k). \quad (8p)$$

The above expressions are then recast as the following set of inequalities

$$\begin{aligned} -\delta_i^{\text{OFF}}(k-1) + \sigma_{\text{OFF},i}^{\text{ON}}(k) &\leq 0, -\delta_i^{\text{ON}}(k) + \sigma_{\text{OFF},i}^{\text{ON}}(k) \leq 0, \delta_i^{\text{OFF}}(k-1) \\ &+ \delta_i^{\text{ON}}(k) - \sigma_{\text{OFF},i}^{\text{ON}}(k) \leq 1; \end{aligned} \quad (9a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} -\delta_i^{\text{OFF}}(k-1) + \sigma_{\text{OFF},i}^{\text{WRM}}(k) &\leq 0, -\delta_i^{\text{WRM}}(k) + \sigma_{\text{OFF},i}^{\text{WRM}}(k) \leq 0, \delta_i^{\text{OFF}}(k-1) \\ &+ \delta_i^{\text{WRM}}(k) - \sigma_{\text{OFF},i}^{\text{WRM}}(k) \leq 1; \end{aligned} \quad (9b)$$

$$\begin{aligned} -\delta_i^{\text{OFF}}(k-1) + \sigma_{\text{OFF},i}^{\text{STB}}(k) &\leq 0, -\delta_i^{\text{STB}}(k) + \sigma_{\text{OFF},i}^{\text{STB}}(k) \leq 0, \delta_i^{\text{OFF}}(k-1) \\ &+ \delta_i^{\text{STB}}(k) - \sigma_{\text{OFF},i}^{\text{STB}}(k) \leq 1; \end{aligned} \quad (9c)$$

$$\begin{aligned} -\delta_i^{\text{CLD}}(k-1) + \sigma_{\text{CLD},i}^{\text{OFF}}(k) &\leq 0, -\delta_i^{\text{OFF}}(k) + \sigma_{\text{CLD},i}^{\text{OFF}}(k) \leq 0, \delta_i^{\text{CLD}}(k-1) \\ &+ \delta_i^{\text{OFF}}(k) - \sigma_{\text{CLD},i}^{\text{OFF}}(k) \leq 1; \end{aligned} \quad (9d)$$

$$\begin{aligned} -\delta_i^{\text{CLD}}(k-1) + \sigma_{\text{CLD},i}^{\text{ON}}(k) &\leq 0, -\delta_i^{\text{ON}}(k) + \sigma_{\text{CLD},i}^{\text{ON}}(k) \leq 0, \delta_i^{\text{CLD}}(k-1) \\ &+ \delta_i^{\text{ON}}(k) - \sigma_{\text{CLD},i}^{\text{ON}}(k) \leq 1; \end{aligned} \quad (9e)$$

$$\begin{aligned} -\delta_i^{\text{CLD}}(k-1) + \sigma_{\text{CLD},i}^{\text{WRM}}(k) &\leq 0, -\delta_i^{\text{WRM}}(k) + \sigma_{\text{CLD},i}^{\text{WRM}}(k) \leq 0, \delta_i^{\text{CLD}}(k-1) \\ + \delta_i^{\text{WRM}}(k) - \sigma_{\text{CLD},i}^{\text{WRM}}(k) &\leq 1; \end{aligned} \quad (9f)$$

$$\begin{aligned} -\delta_i^{\text{STB}}(k-1) + \sigma_{\text{STB},i}^{\text{ON}}(k) &\leq 0, -\delta_i^{\text{ON}}(k) + \sigma_{\text{STB},i}^{\text{ON}}(k) \leq 0, \delta_i^{\text{STB}}(k-1) \\ + \delta_i^{\text{WRM}}(k) - \sigma_{\text{STB},i}^{\text{ON}}(k) &\leq 1; \end{aligned} \quad (9g)$$

$$\begin{aligned} -\delta_i^{\text{STB}}(k-1) + \sigma_{\text{STB},i}^{\text{CLD}}(k) &\leq 0, -\delta_i^{\text{CLD}}(k) + \sigma_{\text{STB},i}^{\text{CLD}}(k) \leq 0, \delta_i^{\text{STB}}(k-1) \\ + \delta_i^{\text{CLD}}(k) - \sigma_{\text{STB},i}^{\text{CLD}}(k) &\leq 1; \end{aligned} \quad (9h)$$

$$\begin{aligned} -\delta_i^{\text{WRM}}(k-1) + \sigma_{\text{WRM},i}^{\text{OFF}}(k) &\leq 0, -\delta_i^{\text{OFF}}(k) + \sigma_{\text{WRM},i}^{\text{OFF}}(k) \leq 0, \delta_i^{\text{WRM}}(k-1) \\ + \delta_i^{\text{OFF}}(k) - \sigma_{\text{WRM},i}^{\text{OFF}}(k) &\leq 1; \end{aligned} \quad (9i)$$

$$\begin{aligned} -\delta_i^{\text{WRM}}(k-1) + \sigma_{\text{WRM},i}^{\text{CLD}}(k) &\leq 0, -\delta_i^{\text{CLD}}(k) + \sigma_{\text{WRM},i}^{\text{CLD}}(k) \leq 0, \delta_i^{\text{WRM}}(k-1) \\ + \delta_i^{\text{CLD}}(k) - \sigma_{\text{WRM},i}^{\text{CLD}}(k) &\leq 1; \end{aligned} \quad (9j)$$

$$\begin{aligned} -\delta_i^{\text{WRM}}(k-1) + \sigma_{\text{WRM},i}^{\text{STB}}(k) &\leq 0, -\delta_i^{\text{STB}}(k) + \sigma_{\text{WRM},i}^{\text{STB}}(k) \leq 0, \delta_i^{\text{WRM}}(k-1) \\ + \delta_i^{\text{STB}}(k) - \sigma_{\text{WRM},i}^{\text{STB}}(k) &\leq 1; \end{aligned} \quad (9k)$$

$$\begin{aligned} -\delta_i^{\text{ON}}(k-1) + \sigma_{\text{ON},i}^{\text{CLD}}(k) &\leq 0, -\delta_i^{\text{CLD}}(k) + \sigma_{\text{ON},i}^{\text{CLD}}(k) \leq 0, \delta_i^{\text{ON}}(k-1) \\ + \delta_i^{\text{CLD}}(k) - \sigma_{\text{ON},i}^{\text{CLD}}(k) &\leq 1; \end{aligned} \quad (9l)$$

$$\begin{aligned} -\delta_i^{\text{ON}}(k-1) + \sigma_{\text{ON},i}^{\text{WRM}}(k) &\leq 0, -\delta_i^{\text{WRM}}(k) + \sigma_{\text{ON},i}^{\text{WRM}}(k) \leq 0, \delta_i^{\text{ON}}(k-1) \\ + \delta_i^{\text{WRM}}(k) - \sigma_{\text{ON},i}^{\text{WRM}}(k) &\leq 1; \end{aligned} \quad (9m)$$

$$\begin{aligned} -\delta_i^{\text{CLD}}(k-1) + \sigma_{\text{CLD},i}^{\text{STB}}(k) &\leq 0, -\delta_i^{\text{STB}}(k) + \sigma_{\text{CLD},i}^{\text{STB}}(k) \leq 0, \delta_i^{\text{CLD}}(k-1) \\ + \delta_i^{\text{STB}}(k) - \sigma_{\text{CLD},i}^{\text{STB}}(k) &\leq 1; \end{aligned} \quad (9n)$$

$$\begin{aligned} -\delta_i^{\text{STB}}(k-1) + \sigma_{\text{STB},i}^{\text{OFF}}(k) &\leq 0, -\delta_i^{\text{OFF}}(k) + \sigma_{\text{STB},i}^{\text{OFF}}(k) \leq 0, \delta_i^{\text{STB}}(k-1) \\ + \delta_i^{\text{OFF}}(k) - \sigma_{\text{STB},i}^{\text{OFF}}(k) &\leq 1; \end{aligned} \quad (9o)$$

$$\begin{aligned} -\delta_i^{\text{ON}}(k-1) + \sigma_{\text{ON},i}^{\text{OFF}}(k) &\leq 0, -\delta_i^{\text{OFF}}(k) + \sigma_{\text{ON},i}^{\text{OFF}}(k) \leq 0, \delta_i^{\text{ON}}(k-1) \\ + \delta_i^{\text{OFF}}(k) - \sigma_{\text{ON},i}^{\text{OFF}}(k) &\leq 1. \end{aligned} \quad (9p)$$

Inequalities (9) will be used as constraints in the proposed MPC controller. It is important to highlight that, for some state transitions, i.e., $\sigma_{\text{ON},i}^{\text{OFF}}(k)$, $\sigma_{\text{OFF},i}^{\text{CLD}}(k)$ and $\sigma_{\text{STB},i}^{\text{OFF}}(k)$, a cost is paid due to the stack degradation in switching from hydrogen production/consumption to no production/no consumption and vice versa. Indeed, each complete cycle of these transactions affects the cycle lifespan of the device. These transitions will be so included in the devices' cost functions while all the inadmissible transitions, i.e., those not shown in Fig. 2, are set

to 0 by means of the constraints that will be also included into the proposed controller.

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{\text{OFF},i}^{\text{STB}}(k) &= \sigma_{\text{OFF},i}^{\text{WRM}}(k) = \sigma_{\text{OFF},i}^{\text{ON}}(k) = \sigma_{\text{CLD},i}^{\text{OFF}}(k) \\ &= \sigma_{\text{CLD},i}^{\text{WRM}}(k) = \sigma_{\text{CLD},i}^{\text{ON}}(k) = \sigma_{\text{STB},i}^{\text{ON}}(k) = \sigma_{\text{STB},i}^{\text{CLD}}(k) \\ &= \sigma_{\text{WRM},i}^{\text{OFF}}(k) = \sigma_{\text{WRM},i}^{\text{CLD}}(k) = \sigma_{\text{WRM},i}^{\text{STB}}(k) = \sigma_{\text{ON},i}^{\text{CLD}}(k) \\ &= \sigma_{\text{ON},i}^{\text{WRM}}(k) = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Operating constraints

Both the electrolyzer and the fuel cell have inherent limitations regarding the switching time between the feasible operating modes. Defining two temporal parameters τ^{CLD} and τ^{WRM} ranging as follows

$$\tau^{\text{CLD}} \in \{k+1, \dots, k+T^{\text{CLD}}\}, \quad (11a)$$

$$\tau^{\text{WRM}} \in \{k+1, \dots, k+T^{\text{WRM}}\}, \quad (11b)$$

the dwelling time in CLD and WRM (needed when switching from OFF to STB, or from STB to ON, respectively) is constrained by

$$\delta_i^{\text{CLD}}(k) - \delta_i^{\text{CLD}}(k-1) \leq \delta_i^{\text{CLD}}(\tau^{\text{CLD}}), \quad (12a)$$

$$\delta_i^{\text{CLD}}(k) + \dots + \delta_i^{\text{CLD}}(k-T^{\text{CLD}}) \leq T^{\text{CLD}}, \quad (12b)$$

$$\delta_i^{\text{WRM}}(k) - \delta_i^{\text{WRM}}(k-1) \leq \delta_i^{\text{WRM}}(\tau^{\text{WRM}}), \quad (12c)$$

$$\delta_i^{\text{WRM}}(k) + \dots + \delta_i^{\text{WRM}}(k-T^{\text{WRM}}) \leq T^{\text{WRM}}. \quad (12d)$$

Interaction with the utility grid

In the scenario under investigation the electricity can be purchased/sold from/to the grid; correspondingly the logical variable $\delta^{\text{grid}}(k)$ is introduced whose activation ($\delta^{\text{grid}}(k) = 1$) or deactivation ($\delta^{\text{grid}}(k) = 0$) depends on the interaction with the grid. The following logical implication is considered

$$[\delta^{\text{grid}}(k) = 1] \Leftrightarrow [P_{\text{grid}}(k) \geq 0], \quad (13)$$

while can be equivalently modeled through the following inequalities

$$\begin{aligned} P_{\text{grid}}(k) &\geq m_{\text{grid}}(1 - \delta^{\text{grid}}(k)), \\ P_{\text{grid}}(k) &\leq (M_{\text{grid}} + \varepsilon)\delta^{\text{grid}}(k) - \varepsilon. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

The auxiliary variables $z^{\text{sale}}(k)$ and $z^{\text{pch}}(k)$ can be defined as

$$z^{\text{pch}}(k) = P_{\text{grid}}(k)\delta^{\text{grid}}(k), \quad (15a)$$

$$z^{\text{sale}}(k) = -P_{\text{grid}}(k)(1 - \delta^{\text{grid}}(k)). \quad (15b)$$

The variables $z^{\text{sale}}(k)$ and $z^{\text{pch}}(k)$ hide a non-linearity in the product of two decision variables which would otherwise make the problem nonlinear. The condition (15) can be recast as

$$\begin{aligned} z^{\text{pch}}(k) &\geq m_{\text{grid}}\delta^{\text{grid}}(k), \\ z^{\text{pch}}(k) &\leq M_{\text{grid}}\delta^{\text{grid}}(k), \\ z^{\text{pch}}(k) &\geq P_{\text{grid}}(k) - M_{\text{grid}}(1 - \delta^{\text{grid}}(k)), \\ z^{\text{pch}}(k) &\leq P_{\text{grid}}(k) + m_{\text{grid}}(1 - \delta^{\text{grid}}(k)); \end{aligned} \quad (16a)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
z^{\text{sale}}(k) &\leq m_{\text{grid}}(\delta^{\text{grid}}(k) - 1), \\
z^{\text{sale}}(k) &\geq M_{\text{grid}}(\delta^{\text{grid}}(k) - 1), \\
z^{\text{sale}}(k) &\geq -P_{\text{grid}}(k) + m_{\text{grid}}\delta^{\text{grid}}(k), \\
z^{\text{sale}}(k) &\leq -P_{\text{grid}}(k) - M_{\text{grid}}\delta^{\text{grid}}(k).
\end{aligned} \tag{16b}$$

The technique adopted for transforming the (nonlinear) mixed product in (15) in the equivalent mixed-linear formulation (16) can be used for the other mixed products; for the sake of brevity, the repetition of such transformation has not been reported for other analogous cases later in the paper.

Ramp up constraints

The constraints

$$|(P_{\text{ez}}(k+1) - P_{\text{ez}}(k))\delta_{\text{ez}}^{\text{ON}}(k)| \leq R_{\text{ez}}, \tag{17a}$$

$$|(P_{\text{fc}}(k+1) - P_{\text{fc}}(k))\delta_{\text{fc}}^{\text{ON}}(k)| \leq R_{\text{fc}}, \tag{17b}$$

limit the slew rate of the electrolyzer input power and of the fuel cell output power so as to avoid damage. The logical power variables $z_{\text{ez}}^{\text{in}}$ and $z_{\text{fc}}^{\text{out}}$ of the electrolyzer and the fuel cell, respectively, can be introduced as

$$z_{\text{ez}}^{\text{in}}(k) = P_{\text{ez}}(k)\delta_{\text{ez}}^{\text{ON}}(k), \tag{18a}$$

$$z_{\text{fc}}^{\text{out}}(k) = P_{\text{fc}}(k)\delta_{\text{fc}}^{\text{ON}}(k). \tag{18b}$$

Following an analogous approach as already done for formulas (15), the mixed product can be equivalently transformed into mixed-linear constraints.

Hydrogen level dynamics

The hydrogen level H in the tank at time instant $k+1$ depends on that at time k , on the efficiencies η_e and η_f of the electrolyzer and of the fuel cell, respectively, on the powers P_{ez} and P_{fc} of the devices in their ON state, respectively, and also on the corresponding logic variables $\delta_{\text{ez}}^{\text{ON}}(k)$ and $\delta_{\text{fc}}^{\text{ON}}(k)$:

$$H(k+1) = H(k) + \eta_e P_{\text{ez}}(k)\delta_{\text{ez}}^{\text{ON}}(k)T_s - \frac{P_{\text{fc}}(k)\delta_{\text{fc}}^{\text{ON}}(k)T_s}{\eta_f}. \tag{19}$$

Notice that, according to (19), the devices produce/consume hydrogen only in their ON modes [24]. Also, notice that the mixed-product can be transformed analogously to what done for formulas (15).

A further dynamic equation of the system can be, in principle, considered. Specifically, both the efficiency of the electrolyzer and of the fuel cell appearing in (19) are subjected to degradation over time. A simple model for this can be the equation

$$\eta_i(k+1) = \left(1 - \frac{d_i}{P_{\text{max}}^{\text{HY}} P_i(k)\delta_i^{\text{ON}}(k)}\right) \eta_i(k), \tag{20}$$

which highlights the dependency of the degradation both on the power and the working hours. Such dynamics, however, take place across longer time-scales than the one considered in this paper for the control of the plant over the prediction horizon, and therefore, in order not to increase the numerical complexity of the MPC, they are not included in the paper by keeping the efficiencies in (19) constant. Notice that this does not exclude the possibility to update their values over time,

when a significant deviation with respect to the current adopted values is measured.

Power balance constraints

In order to achieve a feasible optimal control policy, the energy balance equation must be satisfied at each time-step k :

$$P_w(k) - P_{\text{ez}}(k)\delta_{\text{ez}}^{\text{ON}}(k) + P_{\text{fc}}(k)\delta_{\text{fc}}^{\text{ON}}(k) - P_{\text{avi}}(k) - P_{\text{dump}}(k) + P_{\text{grid}} = 0. \tag{21}$$

The dumping load, although not always present in a generic plant, may be useful in case the plant generation capacity exceeds the transmission lines capacity. For the sake of generality of the modeling, such feature has therefore been included in the power balance equation [45].

Feasibility and physical constraints

The electrolyzer, the fuel cell and the hydrogen tank have operating range limits that can be modeled correspondingly as

$$P_{\text{ez}}^{\text{min}} \leq P_{\text{ez}}(k) \leq P_{\text{ez}}^{\text{max}}, \tag{22a}$$

$$P_{\text{fc}}^{\text{min}} \leq P_{\text{fc}}(k) \leq P_{\text{fc}}^{\text{max}}, \tag{22b}$$

$$H^{\text{min}} \leq H(k) \leq H^{\text{max}}. \tag{22c}$$

As said above, when available, excess power can be dumped rather than shunted towards the downstream hydrogen tank. The benefit is to avoid degradation issues associated with the devices; conversely, the surplus power is lost. The following constraint holds

$$0 \leq P_{\text{dump}}(k) \leq P_w(k), \tag{23}$$

$P_{\text{dump}}(k)$ being a decision variable.

Controller design

In this subsection, various cost functions related to the different requirements of the controller are derived, specifically: the electrolyzer and the fuel cell cost functions; the grid cost function; the local load tracking cost function. The formulation of the MPC is also presented.

Cost functions of the electrolyzer and the fuel cell

The electrolyzer and the fuel cell cost functions include various terms that take into account the aging of the devices, life hours reduction, energy consumption at stand-by state, and the amount of energy spent for cold and warm starts. The proposed cost function addresses all these aspects

$$\begin{aligned}
J_i(k) := & \sum_{j=0}^{T-1} \left(\frac{C_i^{\text{rep}}}{\text{NH}_i} + C_i^{\text{OM}} \right) \delta_i^{\text{ON}}(k+j) + C_{\text{ON},i}^{\text{OFF}} \sigma_{\text{ON},i}^{\text{OFF}}(k+j) \\
& + C_{\text{CLD},i}^{\text{STB}} \sigma_{\text{CLD},i}^{\text{STB}}(k+j) + C_{\text{STB},i}^{\text{OFF}} \sigma_{\text{STB},i}^{\text{OFF}}(k+j) \\
& + [I^{\text{sc}}(k+j) P_i^{\text{STB}} \delta_i^{\text{STB}}(k+j) \\
& + I^{\text{sc}}(k+j) P_i^{\text{CLD}} \delta_i^{\text{CLD}}(k+j) + I^{\text{sc}}(k+j) P_i^{\text{WRM}} \delta_i^{\text{WRM}}(k+j)] T_s,
\end{aligned} \tag{24}$$

where k is the current time instant, $j = 0, 1, \dots, T-1$ accounts for future time instants and $C_{\text{ON},i}^{\text{OFF}}$, $C_{\text{CLD},i}^{\text{STB}}$ and $C_{\text{STB},i}^{\text{OFF}}$ denote the i €

{ez, fc} device cycle costs. Notice that cold starts are usually characterized by higher costs than warm starts and that off devices do not absorb any power.

Cost function for electricity market participation

The cost function modeling the selling and buying energy revenues/costs is given by

$$J_{\text{grid}}(\mathbf{k}) := \sum_{j=0}^{T-1} \left[-I^{\text{sale}}(\mathbf{k}+j)z^{\text{sale}}(\mathbf{k}+j) + I^{\text{pch}}(\mathbf{k}+j)z^{\text{pch}}(\mathbf{k}+j) \right] T_s. \quad (25)$$

Cost function for load tracking

Since one control goal of the proposed controller is tracking a local load demand P_{ref} , the corresponding cost is given by the cumulative squared error between P_{ref} and P_{avl} , i.e.

$$J_{\text{load}}(\mathbf{k}) := \sum_{j=0}^{T-1} (P_{\text{avl}}(\mathbf{k}+j) - P_{\text{ref}}(\mathbf{k}+j))^2. \quad (26)$$

MPC formulation

The proposed MPC provides a trajectory of future control inputs satisfying the system dynamics and constraints and minimizing the microgrid operational costs. At each time instant $k = 0, \dots, T-1$, the controller takes into account the following steps:

1. The system model is initialized to the current values of the hydrogen storage, electrolyzer and fuel cell logical states, states switchings variables and power level;
2. The optimizer calculates the optimal control command sequence over the T horizon by exploiting the renewable generations forecast and the requested user electrical demand along with the upcoming system predicted behaviour. The computed optimal plan provides the decisions on devices logical states, states switchings, storage operations and on grid buying/selling;
3. Only the first sample of the computed control sequence is applied to the plant, and subsequently, the horizon is shifted one step ahead;
4. At time $k+1$ the new system state is measured. By doing so, the forecasts of the electrical reference and the available generation are updated over a rolling window and the MPC problem is solved based on the newly acquired information. One of the key aspects of this receding horizon strategy is the automatic compensation of the disturbances and uncertainties acting on the system because a feedback is practically implemented.

In particular, the state of the system $H(\mathbf{k})$ to be controlled evolves according to (19) and the corresponding state variable is denoted by $H(\mathbf{k}+j)$, with $j > 0$ at time $\mathbf{k}+j$. Let us now introduce the set $\mathcal{C}_{\mathbf{k}}$ of all the decision variable vectors at instant \mathbf{k} defined as

$$\mathcal{C}_{\mathbf{k}} := \left\{ \mathbf{P}_{i,\mathbf{k}}^{T-1}, \mathbf{P}_{\text{avl},\mathbf{k}}^{T-1}, \mathbf{P}_{\text{dump},\mathbf{k}}^{T-1}, \boldsymbol{\delta}_{i,\mathbf{k}}^{\alpha,T-1}, \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\alpha_i,\mathbf{k}}^{\beta,T-1}, \mathbf{z}_{i,\mathbf{k}}^{\geq\gamma,T-1}, \mathbf{z}_{i,\mathbf{k}}^{\leq\bar{\gamma},T-1}, \mathbf{P}_{\text{grid},\mathbf{k}}^{T-1} \right\}, \quad (27)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{P}_{i,\mathbf{k}}^{T-1} &= (P_i(\mathbf{k}), \dots, P_i(\mathbf{k}+T-1))^{\top}, \\ \mathbf{P}_{\text{avl},\mathbf{k}}^{T-1} &= (P_{\text{avl}}(\mathbf{k}), \dots, P_{\text{avl}}(\mathbf{k}+T-1))^{\top}, \\ \mathbf{P}_{\text{dump},\mathbf{k}}^{T-1} &= (P_{\text{dump}}(\mathbf{k}), \dots, P_{\text{dump}}(\mathbf{k}+T-1))^{\top}, \\ \boldsymbol{\delta}_{i,\mathbf{k}}^{\alpha,T-1} &= (\delta_i^{\alpha}(\mathbf{k}), \dots, \delta_i^{\alpha}(\mathbf{k}+T-1))^{\top}, \\ \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\alpha_i,\mathbf{k}}^{\beta,T-1} &= (\sigma_{\alpha_i}^{\beta}(\mathbf{k}), \dots, \sigma_{\alpha_i}^{\beta}(\mathbf{k}+T-1))^{\top}, \\ \mathbf{z}_{i,\mathbf{k}}^{\geq\gamma,T-1} &= (z_i^{\geq\gamma}(\mathbf{k}), \dots, z_i^{\geq\gamma}(\mathbf{k}+T-1))^{\top}, \\ \mathbf{z}_{i,\mathbf{k}}^{\leq\bar{\gamma},T-1} &= (z_i^{\leq\bar{\gamma}}(\mathbf{k}), \dots, z_i^{\leq\bar{\gamma}}(\mathbf{k}+T-1))^{\top}, \\ \mathbf{P}_{\text{grid},\mathbf{k}}^{T-1} &= (P_{\text{grid}}(\mathbf{k}), \dots, P_{\text{grid}}(\mathbf{k}+T-1))^{\top}. \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

Furthermore, let us define the global cost function to be minimized by the MPC controller as

$$J(\mathbf{k}) = \rho_{\text{ez}}J_{\text{ez}}(\mathbf{k}) + \rho_{\text{fc}}J_{\text{fc}}(\mathbf{k}) + \rho_{\text{grid}}J_{\text{grid}}(\mathbf{k}) + \rho_{\text{load}}J_{\text{load}}(\mathbf{k}), \quad (29)$$

the positive weighting factors can be set to obtain a desired prioritization. Therefore, the following MPC problem can be formulated

$$\min_{\mathcal{C}_{\mathbf{k}}} J(\mathbf{k})$$

s.t.

- Discrete logical states (5) – (6),
- Mode transitions (9),
- Storage dynamics (19),
- Grid constraints (16),
- Power balancing equation (21),
- Physical constraints (22) – (23),
- $\delta_i^{\alpha}, \sigma_{\alpha_i}^{\beta} \in [0, 1]$,
- $\alpha, \beta \in \mathcal{A}, \alpha \neq \beta$,
- $z_i^{\geq\gamma}, z_i^{\leq\bar{\gamma}} \in \{0, 1\}$,
- $(\gamma, \bar{\gamma}) \in \mathcal{P}$,
- $\delta^{\text{grid}} \in \{0, 1\}$,
- $i \in \mathcal{I}$.

Since the above problem is solved again at time instant $k+1$, an optimal feedback strategy is generated and applied at run time.

Results analysis and discussion

In this section, the proposed strategy is validated via numerical simulations based on the data of the HAEOLUS plant. Several power production and consumption profiles are considered so as to stress the capability of the controller to address different scenarios. The simulations are preliminary to the implementation of the controller on the plant, whose construction is progressing in parallel to this study. As it will be possible to see, the controller is able to guarantee the satisfaction of the constraints and to achieve the considered control goal committing the equipment and dynamically changing the set points and control variables. It is important to emphasize here that the methodology adopted in the paper

is, in any case, general and not specific to the HAEOLUS plant only.

For the case study at hand, the analysis has been conducted through simulations over a $T = 24$ h horizon with $T_s = 1$ h sampling time according to the nordic electricity market.

As explained above, the purpose is to track the reference power P_{ref} with the available power P_{avl} appropriately via exploiting the wind production, the hydrogen storage capacity and the possibility to sell/buy the power to/from the grid.

The parameters affecting the cost functions used by the optimizer have been chosen as reported in Table 1. The cost of STB to ON transitions (i.e., warm starts) is lower in comparison to that of OFF to ON (i.e., cold starts) or ON to OFF transitions because in STB the stacks of the devices are kept warm thus mitigating their degradation. On the other hand, in STB the devices consume a constant P^{STB} power. The devices' stack replacement costs C_i^{rep} considered in the proposed MPC controller are as 2/3 of the 40% of $Capex_i$ i.e.,

$$C_i^{rep} \approx 0.27 \times Capex_i. \quad (30)$$

Table 1 also reports the $Capex_i$ that have been used.

Suitable weights have been considered to properly combine the different terms of the overall objective function. Such weights have been numerically tuned with a series of simulations to balance the operational costs and the tracking goal satisfaction. Further testing will be executed on the physical plant once the construction and commitment will be terminated.

The MPC controller has been implemented and simulated in MATLAB/YALMIP/GUROBI. Fig. 3 shows the block scheme of the proposed MPC control algorithm. A PC equipped with an Intel Core (TM) i7 – 7700 HQ 2.8 GHz and a RAM capacity of 16 GB is used for the controller computation. The optimization problem is solved, at any step time, in 40 s.

Table 1 – Devices parameters.

PEM Electrolyzer parameters	
$C_{ez}^{STB} = 0.0042 \text{ €}$	$NH_{ez} = 40000 \text{ h}$
$C_{ez}^{ON} = 0.123 \text{ €}$	$C_{ez}^{OFF} = 0.0062 \text{ €}$
$\eta_{ez} = 0.23 \text{ kg/ kW}$	$Capex_{ez} = 1.55 \text{ €/kW}$
$C_{ez}^{OM} = 0.002 \text{ €/ h}$	$p_{ez}^{max} = 3000 \text{ kW}$
$p_{ez}^{min} = 300 \text{ kW}$	$p_{ez}^{STB} = 1 \text{ kW}$
$NY_{ez} = 8000 \text{ h}$	$p_{ez}^{CLD} = 1 \text{ kW}$
$p_{ez}^{WRM} = 1 \text{ kW}$	$N_{ez}^{max} = 5000 \text{ cycles}$
PEM fuel cell parameters	
$C_{fc}^{STB} = 0.003 \text{ €}$	$NH_{fc} = 40000 \text{ h}$
$C_{fc}^{ON} = 0.01 \text{ €}$	$C_{fc}^{OFF} = 0.005 \text{ €}$
$\eta_{fc} = 1.320 \text{ kW/ kg}$	$Capex_{fc} = 1.55 \text{ €/kW}$
$C_{fc}^{OM} = 0.01 \text{ €/h}$	$p_{fc}^{max} = 132 \text{ kW}$
$p_{fc}^{min} = 12 \text{ kW}$	$p_{fc}^{STB} = 1 \text{ kW}$
$NY_{fc} = 8000 \text{ h}$	$p_{fc}^{CLD} = 1 \text{ kW}$
$p_{fc}^{WRM} = 1 \text{ kW}$	$N_{fc}^{max} = 5000 \text{ cycles}$
Hydrogen Tank Parameters	
Volume = 10 kg	Pressure = 30 bar

Fig. 4 shows the requested electric demand and the wind generations considered in the case study, respectively.

In this particular scenario P_{dump} will not be considered for the controlled plant performances, since the surplus power will be either sold to the grid, or shunted towards the electrolyzer for hydrogen production. The latter will therefore act as a backup energy source during low or nearly zero wind hours. By doing so, the power equality constraint (21) will be matched. Table 1 lists the parameters adopted for the study. They are adopted from the preliminary design of the HAEOLUS plant and, for those not defined yet, parameters from the literature have been considered [24,46,47].

Fig. 5(a) shows the system available power, that exactly matches what is required by the electrical load shown in Fig. 4(b). Fig. 5(b) depicts the hydrogen storage level in the hydrogen tank.

The utility grid interaction for electricity buying and selling is shown in Fig. 7(a). It is possible to observe from the figure that over a 24 h horizon, based on the system available power P_{avl} with respect to P_{ref} and the energy storage through the hydrogen, at each time-step the controller takes the decision of energy selling or buying by switching the logical variable δ^{grid} to 1 as shown in Fig. 7(b) (note that, as per formula (13), the case of $P_{grid} = 0$, i.e., no power is either sold or bought, is included in the $\delta^{grid} = 1$). It is observable that the wind power availability with respect to the electric load reference is mostly higher after 12 p.m. The controller, therefore, tends to sell energy to the grid to maximize the revenue. The wind power is available enough to satisfy the electric load, as well as shunted towards the electrolyzer for hydrogen production. The increment in the hydrogen level can be seen in Fig. 5(b) during these hours. It is possible to notice that during the first 3 h, the available wind power is less than the load demand. However, the hydrogen stored in the tank is enough (Fig. 5(b)) to satisfy the load demand through the fuel cell activation. Also, the energy excess after meeting the load demand is sold to the grid during the first three hours.

Between the hours 4–9, the stored hydrogen is at the minimum tank level, as shown in Fig. 5(b). Therefore, the controller sets $\delta^{grid} = 0$, which means energy is bought from the grid, in order to meet the requested load demand during these specific hours. Conversely, during all other hours of the day, P_{avl} exceeds the load, and the surplus energy is sold. Fig. 7(a) shows the energy exchange over 24 h. An increment in the hydrogen level can also be seen from the hours 12–24.

Finally, Fig. 6(a), (c) present the power of the device $i \in \{ez, fc\}$, respectively. The electrolyzer is ON during high wind hours, while the fuel cell as a backup source to the electric load is ON during low or nearly zero wind hours. Fig. 6(b), (d) show the corresponding logic variables associated to the electrolyzer and the fuel cell.

To further illustrate the paper results, the proposed MPC scheme is compared with the relevant strategy in Ref. [21] by Garcia et al. The latter study has been carried out in a

Fig. 3 – Control diagram implementing MPC framework.

Fig. 4 – Wind and operator power profiles.

Fig. 5 – Control response of hydrogen storage system.

laboratory scaled microgrid at University of Seville, Spain and recently published. The authors presented MPC strategies for optimal economic schedule of hydrogen-based microgrids with hybrid energy storage. In addition to presenting the dynamic renewable energy-hydrogen models, the authors also considered the electrolyzer, the fuel cell, the batteries, and the ultra capacitor degradation issues. However, the devices' degradation models are less detailed with respect to what is proposed in this research study and in particular, the authors consider only the degradation issues concerning the devices ON/OFF states. To allow a comparison between the strategy in Ref. [21] and the one

presented in the previous sections, a simulation has been conducted allowing only ON-OFF transitions for the same wind profile and load demand considered in Section Conclusions. Despite the fact that the considered profiles do not present frequent and sharp power imbalances, still the ON-OFF strategy shows that the devices contain one ON-OFF switching more than the strategy in Section Conclusions, as it is possible to see in Fig. 8(a) and (b). For similar wind and load profiles this results in more than three hundred commutations saving per year.

Further benefits of our strategy in conveniently exploiting the stand-by state can be observed for the case of fast power

(a) Electrolyzer power.

(b) Electrolyzer switching states.

(c) Fuel cell Power.

(d) Fuel cell switching states.

Fig. 6 – Control response of the devices.

imbalances or grid islanded mode (for the latter case, the connection terms with the grid are set to null). To show this aspect, the carried out comparison, as shown in Fig. 8(a) and (b), reports the switching response of the proposed controller, while the switching states of the ON-OFF strategy can be observed in Fig. 9(a) and Fig. 9(b). The wind and load demand profiles adopted in simulating the plant in the islanded mode for both approaches are the ones given in Fig. 4(a) and (b), respectively.

(a) Utility grid interaction for energy buying and selling.

(b) Utility grid switching states.

Fig. 7 – Control response of utility grid.

(a) Electrolyzer switching states.

(b) Fuel cell switching states.

Fig. 8 – Control response of the devices (islanded grid).

As it is possible to see from Fig. 9(a), (b), the controller frequently sets the devices in their ON-OFF states, which leads to higher life cycle degradation. Conversely, Fig. 8(a), (b) show the advantages of the strategy proposed in the paper, which is able to set the devices in their stand-by states to keep the devices stacks warm and to avoid cold starts during the hours 6–7, and 10–11 in case of the electrolyzer, and the hours 6 and 20 in case of the fuel cell.

Fig. 9 – Control response of the devices in Ref. [43].

Conclusions

In this paper, novel models for an MPC control strategy of a hydrogen-based ESS integrated in a wind farm are presented. The dynamic models of both devices (the electrolyzer and the fuel cell) map their operating modes with corresponding discrete logical states, together with the continuous dynamics concerning the hydrogen production/consumption.

The proposed MPC scheme takes into account the cost that the electrolyzer and the fuel cell introduce each time they switch between different operating modes, thus decreasing the corresponding number of life cycles and efficiencies. Moreover, all the system operational and physical limitations and maintenance costs, such as the devices power consumptions in their stand-by, cold and warm starts are considered, among the others. The costs related to the operations of each device and the developed mixed-logic dynamic model have been included in an MPC scheme. Simulations have been carried out by tracking a reference power provided by the local load demand, over a 24 h horizon. Correct working operations of both devices and their different operating modes have been validated through numerical results. The latter will be instrumental in the controller implementation of the HAEOLUS plant, currently under construction [14]. Indeed, this work has been developed within the EU2020 funded project HAEOLUS, where the proposed control approach will be implemented on a real hydrogen-based ESS, paired to a wind farm in north Norway. The data employed are based on such a plant and complemented, for those not yet defined, with realistic data from the literature. In conclusion, the main results of the study can be summarized in the following points: i) the development of novel dynamic models for hydrogen-based ESS equipment that take into account the associated working cycle degradation and working

operational modes (combining both continuous state and logical state dynamics); ii) the modeling of low level real-time device features such as cold and warm start; iii) the integration of the developed models into a MDL framework for an MPC strategy to control a target hydrogen storage plant paired with a wind farm (the results are, however, general and applicable to analogous plant devices and to other intermittent renewable sources); iv) the validation of the proposed strategy in a grid connected simulation scenario for revenue generation maximization; v) the correct tracking of the local and contractual user electrical demands.

Future works will integrate the proposed results into a multi-timescale stack power regulation market. Also, other control objective such as pure hydrogen production for commercialization purposes will be investigated as per the goals listed in Ref. [15].

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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